

BLENDDED LEARNING METHOD IN ENGLISH TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Annotation: This article reviews the research related to the use of blended learning in English as a second/foreign language context. Blended learning is a relatively new field that combines traditional learning approaches with distance and online learning. Blended learning (BL) is a popular educational approach that combines online and offline learning to promote active learning and improve student outcomes.

Keywords: blended learning, methods, online, face-to-face learning, ESL and EFL.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматриваются исследования, связанные с использованием смешанного обучения английскому языку как контексту второго/иностранного языка. Смешанное обучение — относительно новая область, сочетающая традиционные подходы к обучению с дистанционным и онлайн-обучением. Смешанное обучение (BL) — это популярный образовательный подход, который сочетает в себе онлайн- и оффлайн-обучение для содействия активному обучению и улучшению успеваемости учащихся.

Ключевые слова: смешанное обучение, методы, онлайн-обучение, очное обучение, ESL и EFL.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ikkinchi/chet til konteksti sifatida ingliz tilida aralash ta'limdan foydalanish bilan bog'liq tadqiqotlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Aralash ta'lim - bu an'anaviy ta'lim yondashuvlarini masofaviy va onlayn ta'lim bilan birlashtirilganga nisbatan yangi soha. Aralash ta'lim (BL) - faol o'rganishni rag'batlantirish va talabalar natijalarini yaxshilash uchun onlayn va oflayn o'rganishni birlashtirilgan mashhur ta'lim usuli.

Kalit so'zlar: aralash ta'lim, usullar, onlayn, yuzma-yuz ta'lim, ESL va EFL.

Introduction: The teaching and learning environment is embracing several innovations, some of which involve using technology through blended learning. This innovative pedagogical approach has been embraced rapidly though it goes through a process. In today's age of developing technologies, great opportunities are being created not only for online teaching but also to face to face learning. As a result, it brings comfort and ease to everyone in the field of education.

Blended learning is a multifaceted educational system that enhances the learning experience and makes education more meaningful. My research on blended learning shows that this method is a combination of techniques that are necessary for different types of education, for example, distance learning is related to computer technologies and is a combination of face-to-face education systems, such as English teaching methodology, educational technology, computer-assisted language learning (CALL), and distance education (Picciano, Dziuban & Graham, 2013).

Blended learning has been defined to differentiate between this teaching and learning mode and traditional or online learning. To illustrate, Bonk and Graham considered blended learning a combination of traditional learning. In another definition, Garrison and Vaughan (2008) indicated that blended learning as a strong combination of face-to-face teaching methods and online teaching systems. That is, they described the class lecture and online education as combining both methods. This education is one of the education systems that are becoming popular day by day and most of the people in the higher educational institutions have also

been enrolled in this education. When describing blended learning, Neumeier (2005) stated that “the most important aim of a Blended Learning design is to find the most effective and efficient combination of the two modes of learning for the individual learning subjects, contexts and objectives.” Significantly, blended learning can be used instead of traditional or online learning because it promotes a stronger sense of engagement and community than traditional face-to-face or fully online teaching and learning methods (Tayebinik & Puteh, 2013).

Blended learning provides additional learning chances that inspire students to engage both in and out of class. Senffner and Kepler (2015) highlighted that blended learning offers a flexible, scalable, and meaningful approach to education. Moreover, Zhang and Zhu (2018) observed that while creating an ideal environment for all students is challenging, blended learning provides a setting that is "accessible, flexible, active, interactive, encouraging, and inspiring" (p. 268). In the context of language education, Neumeier (2005) introduced a framework for developing a blended learning environment. This framework includes six key elements that are essential for crafting a blended learning approach in language education. These elements are mode, model of integration, distribution of learning content and objectives, language teaching methods, participant involvement, and location. These aspects are crucial for language educators to consider when deciding to incorporate blended learning into their instructional methods. Graham, Allen, and Ure (2003, 2005) identified three primary reasons for choosing or designing blended learning over traditional teaching methods: to enhance pedagogical effectiveness, to increase accessibility and flexibility, and to boost cost efficiency. These factors likely contribute to why educators and learners prefer blended learning to conventional methods. Additionally, Graham (2006) described various levels at which blended learning can be implemented, including activity, course, program, and institutional levels, integrating traditional and online teaching elements to varying degrees based on the learning context.

Accurate Reporting and Future Research Suggestions in Research: It's important to report research findings accurately and provide suggestions for future research. Accurate reporting ensures reliable findings, while future research suggestions help advance knowledge and address limitations.

Benefits of Future Research Suggestions:

- **Improved Research Quality:** They identify areas for improvement, leading to higher-quality research.
- **Contribution to the Field:** They suggest new research directions, expanding knowledge.
- **Inspiration for New Ideas:** They spark ideas for further exploration.
- **Guidance for Researchers:** They provide a roadmap for both novice and expert researchers. For example, in blended learning research, future research suggestions might include exploring its effectiveness in different settings and populations, investigating its impact on engagement, and developing new instructional strategies. This study highlights the importance of future research suggestions and provides a collective recommendation on blended learning. It fills a gap in the literature by examining this aspect of research reporting.

Research is becoming a crucial point in blended learning to improve its effectiveness. Studies have shown that blended learning can enhance student success, satisfaction, and sense of community compared to traditional face-to-face courses. Successful blended learning programs require institutional support for course redesign and planning. However, there is still much to learn about the best instructional models and support systems for blended learning. Ongoing research is

needed to explore these areas and address the evolving and complex questions in blended learning. This will help maximize student achievement and success in this increasingly popular educational approach. This study addressed student access by examining success and withdrawal rates in the blended learning courses by comparing them to face-to-face and online modalities over an extended period at the University of Central Florida. Further, the investigators sought to assess the differences in those success and withdrawal rates with the minority status of students. Secondly, the investigators examined the student end-of-course ratings of blended learning and other modalities by attempting to develop robust if-then decision rules about what characteristics of classes and instructors lead students to assign an “excellent” value to their educational experience. Because of the high-stakes nature of these student ratings toward faculty promotion, awards, and tenure, they act as a surrogate measure for instructional quality. Next, the investigators determined the conditional probabilities for students conforming to the identified rule cross-referenced by expected grade, the degree to which they desired to take the course, and course modality.

Picture №1 Blended learning model

The Oxford Group (2013) report noted mixed responses to blended learning, with 16% of learners showing a negative attitude and 26% expressing concerns about course completion. Learner involvement is crucial in any educational process, and their background and characteristics significantly influence their learning effectiveness. In blended environments, the choice of design tools also plays a critical role. This study addresses the effectiveness of blended learning, which previous research has explored in terms of grades, course completion, retention, and graduation rates. However, there is a gap in research concerning the impact of learner characteristics/backgrounds and design features on learning outcomes within the context of Ugandan universities. Furthermore, no studies have examined how these characteristics and design elements predict outcomes based on Guskey's (2000) planning evaluation model, which advocates for evaluation before implementing innovations to identify needs, consider participant characteristics, analyze contextual factors, and collect baseline data. This research is set in a Ugandan university planning to introduce a learning management system (Moodle).

To conclude, the study investigates various learner characteristics such as self-regulation, computer skills, workload management, social and family support, attitudes towards blended learning, gender, and age. It also examines blended learning design features like learner interaction, face-to-face support, learning management system tools, and technology quality. The outcomes considered are learner satisfaction, performance, intrinsic motivation, and knowledge construction. Identifying significant predictors of these outcomes will provide valuable insights for planners to design effective blended learning environments, enhancing this innovative pedagogical approach.

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